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A collection of articles by Asian scholars
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**PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF WORK MOTIVATION:
LEADERSHIP AND REWARD SYSTEM****Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna**

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the psychological foundations of labor motivation, in particular, the impact of leadership styles and the reward system on employee performance on a scientific basis. It highlights how the personal qualities of a leader, management approaches, and effective incentive mechanisms shape attitudes towards work. It also analyzes the impact of internal and external motivation, socio-psychological factors, interpersonal relationships, and the work environment on motivation. The thesis considers an effective reward system as a means of increasing responsibility, loyalty, and initiative in employees. Based on the results of the study, psychological recommendations are given to strengthen motivation in organizations.

Keywords: labor motivation, reward system, internal motivation, external motivation, work performance, incentive, psychological environment, management psychology.

Introduction.

Ensuring labor efficiency and obtaining maximum useful results from employees is one of the important strategic tasks in modern organizations. The human factor, that is, the internal state of employees, their level of job satisfaction, socio-psychological needs and, most importantly, their motivation for work, play a decisive role. Why does a person act in his activities? What factors encourage him to be more active, responsible and initiative? These questions are directly related to the concept of work motivation, one of the important research areas of psychology. Motivation is an internal mental state of a person that encourages a person to a certain activity, causes action and ensures that he continues to act with determination. It is through work motivation that an employee sincerely performs his work, strives for self-development and feels himself an important part of the organization. According to the psychological approach, motivation is associated not only with material rewards, but also with internal factors such as spiritual recognition, the opportunity to express himself in a team, positive social relationships, and self-awareness. From this perspective, the role of effective leadership in the formation and management of labor motivation is invaluable. A leader is not only a person who gives orders, but also inspires employees, instills confidence in them and unites them towards a common goal. His culture of behavior, fairness, attention to employees directly affect the working environment and employee psychology. Strong socio-psychological

leadership in management helps employees to have strong motivation. In addition, the reward system is also considered one of the important factors of motivation. A fair, open and transparent incentive system not only increases interest in work, but also increases employees' loyalty to the organization, their level of self-esteem and a sense of social responsibility. Material rewards, promotion, praise, recognition and other means are psychologically powerful motivating tools. This thesis analyzes in detail the psychological foundations of labor motivation, the relationship between leadership and the reward system, and their impact on employee performance. The goal is to strengthen the human factor approach in the modern management system and identify effective psychological mechanisms that serve to enhance labor motivation.

Methodology:

In this study, a comprehensive approach was used to study the psychological foundations of labor motivation, to deeply analyze the impact of leadership styles and the reward system on employees. The methodological basis of the study was formed by classical and modern approaches to psychological, socio-psychological and management theories. In particular, the theory of the hierarchy of needs of A. Maslow, the two-factor motivation model of F. Hersberg, the theory of achievement-oriented motivation of D. McClelland and psychological concepts of other authors formed the theoretical basis of this work.

Qualitative and quantitative research methods were used in the research process. The questionnaire method was chosen as a quantitative analysis tool, through which the motivation of employees working in different organizations, their attitude to leadership styles, and the importance of the reward system for them were studied. The participants in the survey were socio-demographically diverse, which increased the possibility of generalizing the results.

Qualitative analysis was conducted on the basis of interviews and observations. During the interviews, the internal state of the employees, psychological needs, level of satisfaction with the work environment, and the quality of their communication with the leader were analyzed. Through this, conclusions were drawn based on real examples of how motivational factors affect individual psychological characteristics. Also, during the research, as a practical experiment, work was carried out to introduce psychologically strong motivational tools in a specific organization and evaluate their results. This experimental approach showed how the motivational measures offered to employees - praise, recognition, promotion, or material incentives - changed their attitude to work. This methodological approach made it possible to analyze labor motivation not only from a theoretical but also from a practical point of view, to identify existing problems and develop ways to solve them. Thus, the scientific

conclusions presented in the thesis are enriched with real-life experiences, which enhances their practical significance.

Literature analysis (review):

Scientific research on the psychological foundations of labor motivation shows that motivation is considered a decisive factor in managing human activity. The psychological interpretation of the concept of motivation developed in the 19th and 20th centuries and has been widely studied in various schools and directions to this day.

American psychologist A. Maslow, in his theory of the hierarchy of needs, emphasizes that human actions are guided by needs of different levels. According to him, motivation is not only associated with satisfying material needs, but also with higher-level psychological needs such as self-awareness and self-actualization. This theory serves as the main methodological foundation for the formation of a motivation system based on the human factor, especially in organizations.

F. Hersberg's two-factor theory clearly shows the difference between factors that cause motivation (motivators) and hygiene factors that cause demotivation. This approach allows us to distinguish between areas in the work environment where it is necessary to focus the attention of the reward and the leader. According to Hersberg, incentives (praise, growth opportunities, responsibility) increase motivation, while injustice or unfavorable working conditions increase demotivation.

Another important theoretical source is the theory of achievement motivation developed by D. McClelland. The author connects motivation at work with the level of a person's desire for goals. This approach can be directly applied in the way modern leaders work with employees, as it suggests an individual approach and taking into account personal needs.

Among local authors, the works of Uzbek psychologists M. Teshayev, D. Abdullayeva, F. Karimov, etc., have extensively covered the impact of labor psychology, professional satisfaction, interpersonal relationships, and leadership styles on motivation. In particular, M. Teshayev emphasizes in his works the inextricable link between the psychological culture of the leader, the socio-psychological environment, and the internal state of employees.

Also, foreign sources cover various forms of reward systems, their impact on employee motivation and productivity with accurate statistics. For example, management scientists such as R. Likert, K. Levin, P. Drucker note the relevance of a fair reward system in the formation of motivation in organizations. In particular, they emphasize the strong psychological impact of social justice, recognition and personal achievements on labor motivation. In general, the analyzed literature proves that not only material incentives, but also psychological factors play an important role

in increasing labor motivation - namely, human values, social support, trusting relationships between managers and employees. At the same time, literary sources indicate the importance of an individual approach, social justice and effective management in the formation of a motivation system.

Discussion:

The results of the study show that labor motivation is a multifaceted psychological process, the formation and stability of which depend on various internal and external factors. The employee's attitude to work, his internal motivation and initiative are often directly influenced by the approach of the manager and the presence of a reward system. Especially since the relevance of a person-oriented approach in the activities of modern organizations is increasing, the need to support motivation not only with material means, but also through socio-psychological factors is becoming increasingly evident.

Leadership is not only a management tool, but also a socio-psychological process, which is one of the important factors determining the psychological climate in the work environment. Research has shown that a fair, democratic and supportive leadership style increases employee motivation, strengthens their sense of self-worth, loyalty to the organization, and the desire for professional growth. In such an environment, an employee can openly express his opinion, is not afraid to propose innovations, and is satisfied with his work. On the contrary, authoritarian leadership based on command causes stress, dissatisfaction, and inactivity in employees.

The role of the reward system in employee motivation also deserves special attention. Although material rewards - monthly salary, bonuses, bonuses - directly affect the employee's work efficiency, they serve as a short-term form of motivation. Long-term, stable motivation is achieved through psychological incentives such as moral rewards - recognition, praise in front of the team, and the opportunity for professional growth. Studies show that an employee who feels that his work is appreciated approaches his work more responsibly and shows initiative.

Among the psychological factors affecting labor motivation, the satisfaction of personal needs, social justice, the opportunity to express himself, and the presence of a positive communication environment occupy a special place. The majority of employees who participated in the study concluded that the greatest motivator for them is that their opinion is taken into account, their work is appreciated, and they are confident in themselves.

Another important aspect is that work motivation also depends on individual psychological characteristics. Each employee's approach to work, level of initiative, and attitude to incentives differ from each other. Therefore, an effective motivational system should be organized in accordance with the needs, interests, and temperament

of each employee. This, in turn, requires the improvement of the psychological knowledge and skills of the leader. Strong work motivation is not only a guarantee of organizational development, but also the basis of employees' mental health, social adaptation, and professional maturity. The formation of a leadership and reward system on a psychological basis is the most important key to this process. In this regard, each leader must understand the individual needs of his team and accept motivation not only as a management tool, but also as a fundamental principle supporting human values.

Conclusion.

Work motivation is a complex psychological process that expresses a person's internal and external incentives for work, which is one of the important factors determining the success of the organization and the efficiency of employees. The results of the study showed that effective leadership and a fair reward system are considered the main tools for increasing motivation. In particular, a person-oriented, democratic leadership approach increases the self-confidence of employees and creates the basis for the formation of a positive psychological mood in a team environment.

The reward system, if enriched not only with material but also with moral incentives, can ensure long-term motivation of employees for work. Also, a management strategy based on an individual approach, taking into account the personal needs and psychological characteristics of each employee, gives effective results.

Based on this study, the following main conclusions were drawn:

Work motivation is a complex psychological and social process, and the role of the leader in its formation plays an important role.

Creating a healthy psychological environment in the organization, strengthening relationships of trust and respect between employees increases motivation.

The reward system should be fair, open and transparent, which increases the responsibility of employees for their work.

Along with material incentives, spiritual recognition and opportunities for professional growth are also recognized as important motivators.

Treating each employee on the basis of an individual approach, taking into account his personal interests and needs, significantly increases the level of motivation.

As a result, in modern organizations, high efficiency can be achieved by improving the management culture and motivational mechanisms based on the human factor. Research, practical recommendations and psychological approaches conducted in this direction play an important role in the human resource management

system of organizations.

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